

The First Tibetan Chos-Byung

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The *Chos-byung Mkhas-pa'i dga-ston* of Dpa' bo Gtsug-lag phren-gba (PT) completed in 1565 has unique value among Tibetan histories in recording what are generally accepted as copies of original documents from the time of the early kings which had been preserved at Bsam-yas. They are:

(1) a *bka'-gtsigs*—Edict—by Khri Srong-lde-brtsan that the Buddhist religion should be practised for ever in Tibet; (2) a complementary document, referred to as a *bka'-mchid*, giving an account of the coming of that religion; (3) a copy of the inscription on the *rdo-rings* at Bsam-yas summarising very briefly the purport of the Edict; and (4) a *bka'-gtsigs* by Khri lde-srong-brtsan renewing the vow made by his father. A summary of the edict is inscribed on the Skar-cung *rdo-rings* near Lhasa.

Comparison with the Bsam-yas *rdo-rings* shows that PT's copy is accurate apart from minor orthographical differences; and it may be assumed that similar errors have crept in to the other documents and perhaps also that some difficult passages have been distorted. Further, although PT's copies preserve many archaisms such as the *da-drag* and some of the *ya-btags* in such words as *myi*, *myes*, the reversed *ki-gu* does not appear and more *ya-btags* have probably been omitted than retained. Some names have also been adjusted to modern spelling, e.g. Khri Srong-lde-btsan for *brtsan*; but it can confidently be accepted that the copies are generally accurate representations of 8th and 9th century documents.

They have been published and translated by Professor Tucci in *The Tombs of the Tibetan Kings* (Rome 1950) but that work may not be easily available to Tibetan readers; and Tucci's transliteration, apparently from an indistinct xylograph, contains many errors and omissions. As these documents are the earliest evidence for the practice of Buddhism in Tibet and as their importance seems mostly to have been overlooked by Tibetan scholars, perhaps on account of some undeserved criticism of PT's work in the *Chronicles of the Fifth Dalai Lama*, an accurate transcription may be helpful. I have added a new translation and some historical comment.

In this article I study only nos. 1 and 2. The former is the *bka'-gtsigs*—sworn edict—of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan re-establishing the practice of Buddhism which had been prohibited after the death of Khri lde-gtsug-

brtsan and decreeing that it should continue for ever. After the principal provisions of the edict and again at the end after a list of witnesses, there is the statement: "the text of a *bka'-mchid*, also, showing how the religious law came to the land of Tibet both in earlier and later times has been deposited together (with the edict). Si'i-la varma wrote it".

This second document is introduced by PT with a passage of his own, explaining that "the second *bka'-gtsigs* was written from a copy deposited in the treasury at Dpal Bsam-yas of the text of the history of the coming of the religious law deposited together with the edict, written in the reign of the *btsan-po* Khri Srong-lde-brtsan in letters of *phra-men* and consigned to a golden casket."

The document, as stated in the first *bka'-gtsigs* and as it makes clear itself, is not a *bka'-gtsigs*—a sworn edict—but a *bka'-mchid*—an authoritative exposition. A difference in status may be indicated in that the *bka'-mchid* was written in letters of *phra-men* as against the gold letters of the *bka'-gtsigs*. The reference to Si'-la varma appears to mean that he wrote the *bka'-mchid* rather than that he was the scribe for both texts. At all events, the *bka'-mchid* must have had the full authority of the *btsan-po*. It further explains itself as a *lo-drung* (*sgrung*), a historical account; and while the Bsam-yas *rdo-rings* is the earliest original document to mention Buddhism in Tibet, the *bka'-mchid* together with the *bka'-gtsigs* provide the first evidence in any detail about the history and practice of the faith there. Its introduction is firmly attributed to Khri Srong-brtsan (Srong-brtsan Sgam-po) who founded the Bi-har (vihara) of Ra-sa; there is no mention of Lha Tho-tho-ri.

The date of the documents must be between the completion of the *gtsug-lag-khang* of Bsam-yas and the year 782 A.D. in which as can be seen from the T'ang Annals, Mchims Zhang Rgyal-zigs shu-theng who was Chief Minister at the time of the Edict, was dismissed from that office. The period can be greatly narrowed if 779 A.D. be accepted as the year in which the temple of Bsam-yas was completed. The Edict shows that some months after Khri Srong-lde-brtsan, who was born according to the Tibetan Annals from Tun-huang in 742 A.D., attained the age of twenty, steps were taken to re-establish the practice of Buddhism. The Annals also show that there was a considerable reorganization of the government in 763. The *bka'-mchid* relates that the *gtsug-lag-khang* of Bsam-yas was consecrated for use (*rten btsugs*) in the spring of a sheep year. The first such year after 762 was 767 A.D.; but it is probable that a much longer time would be needed to consolidate the restored religion, invite teachers from outside Tibet, choose and prepare the site and complete the great building. The year 779 A.D. is therefore more likely.

The number of religious institutions to which copies of the edicts were sent, not only in Lhasa and at Bsam-yas but from Gilgit to the China border, shows a widespread practice of Buddhism throughout the Tibetan empire by 782 A.D.—well before the great debate between rival champions of Indian and Chinese doctrines which probably took place about 792 A.D. (see P. Demiéville, *Le Concile de Lhasa*, Paris 1952 and G. Tucci, *Minor Buddhist Texts II*. Rome 1958).

In the Edict the Btsan-po binds by his oath not only himself and his son but also the mother of the son (or sons). From the Tibetan Annals it is seen that a son was born to Khri Srong-lde-brtsan in 760 A.D. This was probably the eldest son Mu-khri who according to PT *ja* 126 a. was the first of four and who died young. I suggest he was the son of queen Rgyal-mo-brtsan of 'Bro who together with her son dedicated the great bell at Bsam-yas in honour of her husband and who later became a nun with the name Jo-mo Byang-chub, perhaps because of the death of her only son. She was, also, a patron of the Chinese teacher Mahayana in the great religious debate; and she dedicated another bell—at Khra-'brug—in the reign of Khri lde-srong-brtsan. The other sons of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan who eventually succeeded him were born to another queen, the lady of Tshes-pong, beginning with Mu-ne, probably in 774 A.D. It is not certain whether *sras* and *yum* in the edict refer specifically to one son and one mother or to sons and mothers.

Apart from historical information the documents also embody in simple terms what were accepted in the eighth century as the essential elements of Buddhist practice; and it is interesting that Nepal (Lho-bal) is described as the immediate source of that practice.

The following is a translation from the *Chos-byung* of Dpa'bo gtsug-lag vol. *ja* ff 108 b to 111 b. of which a transcription is appended.

“Formerly Ma-zhang grom-pa-skye and others took pains to destroy the religious law; and so that such a thing might not happen in future it was prohibited by a solemn oath and by an edict that no Tibetan should destroy the religious law. Two edicts were made to that effect. This is the first:

“This is written as a copy from the text deposited in the treasury of the temple of Bsam-yas Lhun-gyis grub-pa written in the reign of the btsan-po Khri Srong-lde-brtsan and consigned to a golden casket.

A copy of the edict in the casket made so that the three jewels should never be abandoned and never destroyed. In accordance with the principal intention of the command of the Buddha (Tathagata) if one does not comprehend the truth in one's mind, the three worlds even become a

place of misery. There is no one who has not been born before. Having been born he acts with purpose or without. Then he dies. And having died he is born again in a good or a bad situation. Further, the one who teaches the good is the Buddha. That which perceives clearly is the text of the religious law. That which shows the way to virtue is the community of monks. These are a sure refuge and as good as an island. When by the increasing blessing of the three jewels in the time of my ancestors heretofore, they acted in each generation according to the custom, there really were temples both new and old. After the *btsan-po*, my father, went to heaven, as there were precedents for removing dissension,¹ the text was recorded of an edict sworn solemnly on oath by the *btsan-po* father and son, the mother of the son, and the ministers of the exterior and interior both great and small, that since the time when the *gtsug-lag-khang* of Bsam-yas Lhun-gyis-grub was consecrated² on the seventh day of the spring month of the sheep year, from then onwards in Tibet the practice of the religious law of the Buddha together with the shrines³ of the three jewels should never be abandoned and never destroyed.

There being the 'Phrul-snang temple of Ra-sa, the temple of the Rgya-btags Ra-mo-che,⁴ Bsam-yas Lhun-gyis-grub temple of Brag-dmar and the temple of Khams-sum Mi-ldog-sgröl⁵ and so on, let the people of Tibet from the highest downwards establish shrines of the three jewels and entering on deliverance from their deeds, act so that this practice of the religious law of the Buddha shall never be abandoned and never destroyed. Let them enter on deliverance from their deeds.

And let them act so that property designated for providing requisites for the worship of the three jewels shall never be diminished and never decreased. From henceforward in every generation let the *btsan-po*, father and son in person swear an oath in this way and let the chief ministers also take the oath.

And invoking as witnesses to the oath thus made all the Buddhas of the ten directions, all of the holy law, all the community of the enlightened, the Self-perfected Buddhas, the disciples, whatever order of gods there are in heaven and earth, the personal gods of Tibet, all the nine gods, and all the nagas, demons and spirits, let it be made known that this edict is unalterable. Further, if anyone does not act in accordance with the edict and subverts the three jewels or violates the oath, let him be born as a creature in hell. But if anyone acts in accordance with it, let him become manifestly a Buddha in truly perfected enlightenment than which there is nothing higher.

Also, the text of an authoritative account of how the religion of the Buddha came to Tibet both in earlier and later times, has been deposited together with the edict.

Thirteen copies like this have been written. One has been placed in the archives. Two have been sealed and one each deposited with the religious communities of the 'Phrul-s nang temple of Ra-sa and the Bsamyas Lhun-gyis grub temple of Brag-dmar. Ten copies have been sealed at the end and one each has been given to the 'Phrul-s nang temple of Ra-sa, the temple of Bsamyas Lhun-gyis-grub, the temple of Bkra-shis lha-yul of Khra-'brug, the religious community of the Palace, to the Rgyabtags Ra-mo-che of Ra-sa, Khams-sum Myi-l dog-sgrol of Brag-dmar, to the country of Bru-sha, the country of Zhang-zhung, to Mdo-smad and to the jurisdiction of Sde-blon,⁶ to be held by the religious community of their temples.

Those who swore the oath were: The Dbon⁷ A-zha-rje, the great ministers of the council, the great minister Zhang Rgyal-gzigs⁸ shu-theng,⁹ Blon Stag-sgra klu gong, Zhang Rgyal-tshang lha-s nang etc.

(51 persons in all including groups of inner ministers, outer ministers the governors of Mdo-smad (*sa-la-dbang-po*) and generals.)

The text of the authoritative account of how the religious law came to Tibet both in early and later times has also been deposited together. Brang-ti Shi'-la-varma wrote this'.

So it was written. As for the second *bka'-gtsigs*, it is written as a copy from the text of the history of the coming of the religious law kept together with the edict. In the reign of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan it was written in *phra-men* and having been consigned to a golden casket was deposited in the treasury of Dpal Bsamyas.

'A copy of the text of the history of the practice of the religion of the Buddha together with the shrines of the three jewels in Tibet from early times until the present which is kept in the casket.

From the time when the religion of the Buddha was first practised with the building of the Bi-har¹⁰ of Ra-sa in the reign of the fourth ancestor Khri Srong-brtsan down to the practice of the religion of the Buddha with the building of the temple at Kwa-chu in Brag-dmar in the reign of the father, Khri Lde-gtsugs-brtsan five generations have passed.

After the *btsan-po* the father went to heaven some of the ministers actively conspiring together destroyed the practice of the religion of the Buddha which had been continuous from the time of the ancestors. Then they vilified it, saying that the gods and the religion of Nepal were not right and further, they wrote a law that from then onwards no one should practice it.

After that when the present *btsan-po* attained the age of twenty, at first there were bad prognostications and some evil omens; and because, whatever rituals were performed to interpret them, the bad prognostications and evil omens continued for many months, there was therefore rejection of the law against the practice of the religion of the Buddha and it was not obeyed; and when it was said that worship should be made to the three jewels immediately everything turned to good.

Then with the help of teachers of virtue the religious law was heard and texts were also brought forth to be seen; and there was deliberation how the religion of the Buddha should be practised increasingly. At that time some people following the bad practices of the old religion of Tibet were addicted to all sorts of bad actions such as worshipping the personal gods¹¹ and using improper rites. Some were addicted to colouring their bodies red, some to casting spells¹² upon the government, some to causing diseases of men and cattle and some to causing famine to break out.

Looking into the religious law itself: if the effects of the religious law did not exist in the worldly sphere, countless numbers of living creatures would be born into the four kinds of existence and would transmigrate in whichever cycle they were involved, without beginning and without end. Existence is according to one's former deeds. Whatever one does well in body, speech, or mind becomes virtue; whatever evil one does becomes sin; whatever is neither good nor bad is indeterminate. The fruit of what one does to others ripens for oneself. Birth as god in the spheres of heaven, as a man on earth, a *lha-ma-yin*, or a *yi-dags*, or as an animal in hell below the earth, whichever of these six states in which one is born comes from one's past actions. Those who have transcended the world and have become victorious Buddhas, the spiritually enlightened Bodhisattvas, those who win enlightenment for themselves, and the disciples who attain perfection gradually, all those have attained that state by amassing for themselves an accumulation of merit and knowledge. That is how it is explained. If it be asked what is virtue, it is the ten virtuous actions and so on. If it be asked what is not virtue, it is the ten unvirtuous actions and so on. If it be asked what is an indeterminate action, it is the four ways of behaviour and so on. If it be asked what are the accumulations of world-transcending merit and knowledge, they are, in addition to the ten virtues, the four truths, the twelve elements that arise from the accumulation of causes, the thirty-seven principles leading to enlightenment and the ten surpassing perfections and so on. The fruits that come from these are the four kinds of absence from fear, the four true forms of knowing, the ten powers, the eighteen unmixed attributes, and the thirty-two compassions and so on. The detailed explanation is found in the writings of the religious law.

If all these precepts arising from the religious law are followed, some

persons, by immediate discrimination between the good and the harmful, realize it clearly. Some who do not realize it immediately, by taking the measure of the nature of those who have passed beyond them become able to grasp it with certainty and by applying themselves to these scriptures will in every way come to know whether this religious law should be cast aside or should be practised.

The minor princes under our dominion, the A-zha ruler and so on, and the ministers of the exterior and the interior have been consulted and a counsel was held and they considered in brief these things together, first that trust should be put in the commandments of the Buddha, secondly that the example of the father and ancestors should be followed; and thirdly that help should be given by the power of the teachers of virtue. So increasing counsel was taken over and above the advice that those addicted to what is not virtuous and not good should not act in that way; and when it was asked how the purpose for good might not be changed and how it might be increased, an excellent summary of the religious law was made. Further it was said that in three ways great importance should be attached to not harming it: first, since it is the realization of the highest purpose, no harm must be done to the full extent of its good; secondly, looking to this infinite advantage for everyone, it is not right to destroy the need for it by some sensory standards; and thirdly since our ancestors have practised it for many generations it cannot be anything but good. By such counsels men were converted to its practice. In view of this, with regard to the practice of the religion of the Buddha, first, everyone was devoted to it as the good; and secondly, being made suspicious by former instances of its destruction, a solemn oath never to destroy it was recorded in writing, and action was taken so that henceforward in each generation, also, the vow should be made and it should be sworn to by all from the ministers downwards. Thus it was said. And these documents in full were deposited in the treasury; and the text of the edict inscribed in short on the *rdor ring* at Bsam-yas is as follows:¹³...

Mkhas pa'i dga' ston ja f.108 b.

sngon ma zhang grom pa skyes la sogs pas chos bshig pa thugs
bcags nas phyin chad de lta bu mi 'byung ba' i phyir bod sus kyang chos
mi bshig pa'i bka' gtsigs bcas / dbu snyung bzhes mna' bsgags te de
'dra ba lan gnyis mdzad pa'i bka' gtsigs dang po ni / / btsan po khri
srong lde btsan gyi sku ring la / shog bu thing ga la gser gyis bris nas /
gser gyi sgrom bur bstsal pa'i bka' gtsigs kyi yi ge bsam yas lhun gyis grub
pa'i gtsug lag khang gi dkor mdzod tu bzhag pa las dpe' bgyis te bris pa/
/ / dkond cog gsum nam du yang mi btang ma zhib par dgyi ba'i gtsigs
sgrom bu nang na mchis pa'i dpe' / de bzhin gshegs pa'i bka' las 'byung
ba don thog du sbyar na / yang dagpa nyid khong du ma chud pas kham
sum yang sdug sngal gyi gnas su gyur / thams cad kyang gna' nas ma

skyes pa med / skyes nas ni don dang don med par spyod / de nas kyang
 shi bar 'gyur / shi nas kyang gnas bzang ngan du phyir skye / de la legs
 su ston pa ni sangs rgyas / mngon par dmigs pa ni chos kyi yi ge / dge
 bar mtshon pa ni dge 'dun rnams te / gtan gyi skyabs dang gling du bzang
 ngo // dkong cog gsum ni byin du ched che ste / yab mes snga ma kun
 gyi ring la yang gdung rabs re re zhing lugs su mdzad ste / gtsug lag khang
 gsar rnying dngos yod pa yin / btsan po yab dgung du gshegs pa'i phyi
 nas / pan pun khyer pa'i dpe tshul yod pa nas / gtsug lag khang lhun gyis
 grub tu / lug gi lo la dpyid zla ra ba'i tshes bcu bdun la rten btsugs pa'i
 tshe / da bas phan chad / bod yul du dkond cog gsum rten bcas te / sangs
 rgyas kyi chos mdzad pa mi gzhig par (f 109 a) // btsan po yab sras
 dang sras kyi yum gyis dbu snyung bzung zhing yi dam bcas pa dang /
 phyi nang gi blon po che phra mtha' dag bro stsal ba'i gtsigs kyi yi ger
 bris pa'o //

/ ra sa'i 'phrul snang gtsug lag khang dang rgya btags ra mo che'i gtsug
 lag khang dang / brag dmar gyi bsam yas lhun gyis grub kyi gtsug lag
 khang dang kham s gsum mi ldog sgrol gyi gtsugs lag khang la stsogs te /
 bod kyi rigs su bla nas / dkond cog gsum gyi rten btsugs te / bod las
 kyang thar par gzud cing / sangs rgyas kyi chos mdzad pa 'di nam du
 yang / mi gtang ma zhid par dgyi'o bod las thard par gzud to // / stsug
 lag khang de rnams su dkond mchog gsum gyi yo byad sbyor ba'i rkyend
 kyang ran pa 'os par dpags te bla nas phul ba las / nam zhar kyang mi
 dbri mi bskyung bar bgyis so // da phyin chad gdung rabs re re yang /
 btsan po yab sras 'di bzhin du yi dam bca' zhing zhal gyis bzhes par
 bgyi'o // blon po thog thog kyang bro stsal bar bgyi'o / / 'di ltar yi dam
 bcas pa / phyogs bcu'i sangs rgyas thams cad dang dam pa'i chos thams
 cad dang / byang chub sems dpa'i dge 'dun thams cad dang / rang sangs
 rgyas dang nyan thos thams cad dang / gnam sa'i rim pa lha'o cog dang /
 bod yul gyi sku lha dang/ lha dgu thams cad dang / klu dang / gnods byin
 dang mi ma yinpa thams cad dpang du gsol ste / gtsigs 'di lasmi 'gyur
 bar mkhyen par bgyis so // de la gtsigs ltar ma bgyis te / dkond cog gsum
 gyi sku bslus sam mna' kha dbud bgyis na / sems can dmyal bar skyes
 shig / 'di bzhin du mdzad cing bgyis na / thams cad kyang bla na med
 pa yang dag par rdzogs pa'i byang chub tu mngon par sangs rgyas par
 shog cig // (109 b)

/ sangs rgyas kyi chos bod yul du / snga phyir ji ltar byung ba'i
 bka' mchid kyi yi ge gcig kyang zla la bzhag go //

/dpe 'di 'dra ba bcu gsum bris te / gcig ni phyag sbal na bzhag go
 gnyis ni phyag rgyas btad ste / ra sa'i 'phrul snang gtsug lag khang dang /
 brag dmar gyi bsam yas lhun gyis grub kyi dge 'dun la re re bzhag go /
 bcu ni mthar phyag rgyas btad ste / ra sa'i 'phrul snang gtsug lag khang
 dang / bsam yas lhun gyis grub kyi gtsug lag khang dang / khra 'brug gi
 bkra shis lha yul gtsug lag khang dang / pho brang 'khor gyi dge 'dun

dang / ra sa'i rgya btags ra mo che dang / brag dmar gyi khams sum mi
ldog sgrol dang / bru sha yul dang / zhang zhung yul dang / mdo smad
dang / sde blon ris dang / 'di rnam kyis gtsug lag khang gi dge 'dun la dpe
re re 'chang du stsald to / /

/bro stsald pa la / / dbon a zha rje / / zhang blon chen po
bka' la gtogs pa la / / blon chen po zhang rgyal gzigs shu theng blon
stag sgra klu gong / zhang rgyal tshan lha snang / etc etc.

... f 110a line 2 chos bod yul du snga phyir ji ltar byung ba'i bka'
mchid kyis yi ge gcig kyang zla la bzhag go / brang ti sh'i la warmas
bris / zhes byung ngo / / bka' gtsigs gnyis pa ni / btsan po khri srong lde
btsan gyi sku ring la / chos 'byung ba'i lo drung gi yi ge zla la bzhag pa /
phra men gyis bris te gser gyi sgrom bur stsal nas / dpal bsam yas kyis dkor
mdzod tu bzhag pa las dpe' bgyis nas bris pa / /

/ gna' da 'chad bod yul du dkond cog gsum gyi rten bcas te /
sangs rgyas kyis chos mdzad pa'i lo drung gi yi ge bris pa / sgrom bu'i nang
na mchis pa'i dpe' / /

/ btsan po bzhi mes khri srong btsan gyi ring la / ra sa'i bi har
brtsigs te sangs rgyas kyis chos thog ma mdzad tshun chad / btsan po yab
khri lde gtsug brtsan gyi ring la / brag dmar gyi kwa chur gtsug lag khang
brtsigs te sangs rgyas kyis chos mdzad phand chad gdung rabs lnga lon
no / / / btsan po yab dgung du gshegs kyis 'og du zhang blon kha cig
gis hur 'dums kyis blo zhig phyung ste / yab mes kyis ring tshund chad /
sangs rgyas kyis chos mdzad mdzad pa yang bshig go / de nas yang snyed ni
lho bal gyis lha dang chos bod yul du bgyi ba'i myi rigs shes / gzhan yang
phyind chad bgyid tu mi gnang bar bka' khrims bris so / /

/ de nas btsan po zha snga nas lo nyi shu bzhes pa na / thog ma
ni phyag spring dang ltas shig ngan te / cho ga ci mdzad pas bshad kyang
/ dgung zla du mar phyag spring (f 110 b) dang ltas ngan nas / sangs rgyas
kyis chos bgyid du mi gnang ba'i bka' khrims kyang khrims su mi bgyi
bar dor / dkond cog gsum gyi mchod pa yang bgyi zhes bgyis na gzod
bzang por gyurd to / /

de nas dge ba'i bshes gnyen gyis bstangs te chos kyang gsan /
yi ge yang spyang sngar brims nas / sangs rgyas kyis chos dpel zhing mdzad
par sgroms so / / de na bod kyis chos rnying pa ma lags la / sku lha gsol
ba dang cho ga myi mthun pas / kun kyang ma legs su dogs te / la la ni sku
la dmar yang dogs / la la ni chab srid gong gis kyang dogs / la la ni mi nad
phyugs nad byung gis kyang dogs / la la ni mu ge langs bab kyis kyang
dogs so (mu ge dang sad ser bah kyis ms) / /

/ chos nyid kyis nang du brtags na / chos las 'byung ba ni 'jig rten

gyi khams su myed pa na / sems can gyi khams grangs med pa / skye ba
 rnam bzhi'i nang du skye zhing 'khor ba la gtogs so cog / dang po'i thog
 ma med pa nas / tha ma'i mtha' myed pa'i bar du / rang gi las kyis de
 bzhin du srid pa las / lus dang ngag dang yid gsum nas legs gi las kyis
 de bzhin du srid pa las / lus dang ngag dang yid gsum nas legs par spyad
 to cog ni dge bar 'gyur / nyes pa spyed to cog ni sdig par 'gyur / legs nyes
 med pa ni lung du myi ston par 'gyur / gzhan la phar byas pa'i 'bras bu ni
 bdag la smind te / gnam gyi rim pa'i lhar skye ba dang / sa'i steng gi myi
 dang / lha ma yin dang / yi dags dang / byol song dang / sa'i 'og gi sems
 can dmyal ba dang / 'di drug du skye 'o cog kyang rang gi las kyis 'gyur
 ro/ /'jig rten las 'das te sangs rgyas bcom ldan 'das su 'gyur ba dang /
 byang chub sems dpa' dang rang byang chub dang / nyan thos kyis rim par
 'grub pa kun kyang bsod nams dang ye shes kyi tshogs rang gis brtsogs pa
 las 'gyur ro zhes 'byung ngo // dge ba gang zhe na dge ba bcu la bstogs
 pa'o / myi dge ba gang zhe na / mi dge bcu la bstogs pa'o // lung du mi
 ston pa gang zhe na / spyod lam bzhi la bstogs pa'o // 'jig rten las 'das
 pa'i bsod nams dang ye shes kyi tshogs gang zhe na / dge ba bcu'i steng
 du bden pa bzhi dang / rkyen dang 'du ba tshogs ste byung ba'i yan lag
 bcu gnyis dang / byang chub kyi phyogs kyi chos sum bcu rtsa bdun dang
 pha rold tu phyind pa bcu la bstogs pa'o // de'i 'bras bu ni mi 'jigs pa
 bzhi dang / so so yang dag par shes pa bzhi dang / stobs bcu dang / ma
 'dres pa'i chos bco brgyad dang / thugs rje chen po sum bcu rtsa gnyis la
 bstogs par 'gyur te / gtan tshigs zhib tu ni chos kyi yi ge'i nang na mchis
 so //

/ chos kyi nang nas byung ba 'di rnams rjes bca'd na / kha cig ni
 legs nongs kyis dmyigs 'phral du mngon pa yang mchis / kha cig 'phral du
 mi mngon pa yang mngon par gda' ba rnams kyi tshul las dpags na / nges
 par gzung du rung ba yang mchis te / mdo de rnams dang sbyar na / chos
 'di gtang ngam mdzad dam ci rigs shes / 'bangs su mnga' ba rgyal phran
 'a zha rje la bstogs pa dang phyi nang gi blon po rnams la bka's rmas /
 bka' gros su mdzad nas / gcig tu na sangs rgyas bcom ldan 'das kyi bka'
 lung la bsten / gnyis su na yab mes kyi dpe lugs la 'tshal / gsum du na dge
 ba'i bshes gnyen gyi mthus bstangs pa dang yang sbyar nas mdor brtags na
 / myi dge ma legs par dogs pa'i rnams kyang de ltar myi 'gyur gyi steng
 du / ched che bar bka' gros mdzed to / de lam legs par ni ji ltar myi 'gyur
 ched ni ji ltar che zhe na / chos kyi mdo ni legs su bgyi bas /bla na med
 pa'i don bsgrub pa lags te / legs pa'i mtha' nongs par myi 'gyur gyis gcig /
 thams cad la yun du dpen pa 'di lta'o // tshor dpags tsam gyis dgos pa
 gzhi'g du myi rung gis gnyis / yab mes gdung rabs du ma'i bar du mdzad
 kyang / ma legs pa ma byung ba dang gsum gyis da yang nongs par myi
 'gyur la ched che'o zhes // mdzad par bka' gros btul te mdzad to // de
 lta bas na sangs rgyas kyi chos mdzad pa yang / gcig du na yong gis bzang
 la gces / gnyis su na sngon bshig pa'i dpe' byung bas thugs yid dogs te
 brtan du mi gzhi'g par dbu snyung bro mna' bor ba yang yi ger bris so //

phyind cad kyang gdung rabs gcig cing / yi dam mdzad pa dang blon po
 man cad kyang bro stsal bar bgyis so/ / zhes byung ngo 'di dag ni rgyas pa
 dkor mdzod du bzhag pa yin la / mdor bsdus bsam yas kyi rdo ring la
 brkos pa'i gtsigs yig ni.....

notes and references

1. The passage is somewhat obscure. Tucci appears to take *pan pun* as *phan tshun*; but *phan phun* is found in the Zhwa'i inscription and elsewhere with the meaning "dissension, disagreement".
2. I take *rten btsugs*, "establishing the *rten*" as similar to *rab gnas*.
3. *rten*, "support, container" covers images, books and other religious objects. "Shrine" may not be strictly accurate but it is difficult to find a single satisfactory word.
4. the Rgya-btags Ra-mo-che (belonging to the Chinese?) was most probably founded by Kim-sheng Kong-co, the Chinese bride of Khri Lde-gtsug-brtsan who came to Tibet in 710 (see the 8th/9th century *Li Yul Chos-kyi Lo-rgyus* 1.58. Emmerick, *Tibetan Texts Concerning Khotan*, 1967.
5. The Khams-sum Mi-ldog-sgrol temple at Bsam-yas is attributed to Khri-Srong-lde-brtsan's queen Tshes-pong Rma-rgyal ldong-skar.
6. Sde-blon is probably an error for Bde-blon, a high official established in the reign of Khri Srong-lde-brtsan to control several districts (*mthong-khyab*) in the China border region.
7. Although there was a formal *dbon-zhang* relationship between the A-zha ruler and the Tibetan *btsan-po* in virtue of the marriage of a Tibetan princess to the A-zha-rje in 689, it is probable that the reading should be *Bon* which is much more commonly used in Tun Huang *mss* and perhaps is a tribal name. E. H. Parker in *A Thousand Years of the Tartars* cites a Hwun section of the Tu-yu-hun (A-zha).
8. The name in early orthography is Rgyal-zigs.
9. In the Zhol inscriptions etc. the name is Stag-sgra klu-khong.
10. Bi-har—vihara. In PT's copy of the edict of Khri Lde-srong-brtsan (f 128 b. it appears as Dpe-har).
11. *sku lha* here and also in the Edict, may be PT's emendation of

sku-bla the cult deity of the Tibetan kings, see A Macdonald, *Études Tibétaines*, 1971, pp. 297-309.

12. *gong* here should perhaps read '*gong*.
13. The Inscription on the Bsam-yas *rdo-ring* has been published by Tucci in *Tombs of the Tibetan Kings* pp. 94-95.